

Diffusion-NMR Meets Hybrid Chiral Micelles: A New Route to Enantiomeric Differentiation

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Enantiomers are chiral molecules that exist as non-superimposable mirror images of each other. These compounds are of great importance in fields such as pharmaceuticals, food, and materials science due to their unique interactions with other chiral entities, which can result in distinct biological or physicochemical properties. Differentiating enantiomeric mixtures is crucial for the development and application of these compounds, but it remains a significant challenge in analytical and physicochemical sciences. Matrix-Assisted DOSY (MAD) using chiral resolving agents (CRAs) is a promising approach for evaluating enantiomeric mixtures through diffusion-NMR. However, current implementations face limitations, including high CRA costs, limited availability, and subtle diffusion separation, often within the experimental error margin. [1,2] To overcome these issues, this study investigates a hybrid chiral matrix composed of reverse micelles formed by the cationic surfactant (-)-DMEB in combination with either (*R*)-BINOL or (*S*)-BINOL to enhance enantiomeric discrimination of mandelic acid (MA). Samples containing 40 mM of MA, varying concentrations of BINOL, and 150 mM of DMEB in 500 μ L of CDCl₃ were prepared. ¹H diffusion-NMR experiments were performed using the Oneshot pulse sequence on a 600 MHz spectrometer at 25 °C. Overall, the results revealed that systems containing only BINOL or DMEB exhibited enantiomeric differentiation in the frequency domain but no diffusion separation. Interestingly, the hybrid system containing (*S*)-BINOL and (-)-DMEB enabled both frequency and diffusion separation of the MA enantiomers, exhibiting stereoselectivity for the (*R*)-MA enantiomer. In contrast, the combination of (*R*)-BINOL and DMEB failed to achieve such separation, indicating that the enantiodiscrimination ability of the hybrid matrix depends strongly on the BINOL configuration. Titration experiments revealed stronger interactions between (*R*)-BINOL and DMEB and confirmed BINOL's localization in the micelle's polar region. In the presence of MA, (*S*)-BINOL consistently enhanced enantiomer frequency separation in all studied concentrations, whereas (*R*)-BINOL displayed a competition effect with DMEB, preventing efficient separation for some range of BINOL amounts. Overall, this study demonstrates that tuning the matrix composition in hybrid chiral micellar systems can significantly impact enantiodiscrimination performance. These findings highlight a promising, cost-effective, and adaptable strategy for probing chiral interactions and enhancing stereochemical analysis using diffusion-NMR.

1. Cabral, TLG, et al. *Angew. Chem.*, 137, 5, e202418508, **2025**.

2. Cabral, TLG, et al. *Chem. Eur. J.*, 31, 25, e202404694, **2025**.

Acknowledgments: FAPESP grant #2020/10246-0, #2021/05081-5 and #2023/07116-6.